

LOWER BOUNDS FOR NUMBERS WITH THREE PRIME FACTORS

Paul Kinlaw

Department of Mathematics, Husson University, Bangor, Maine
KinlawP@husson.edu

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Abstract

A *k*-almost prime number is a product of *k* prime numbers, some of which may be repeated. By a 1900 theorem of Landau, the number of *k*-almost prime numbers not exceeding *x* is asymptotic to $x(\log \log x)^{k-1}/((k-1)!\log x)$. We prove a numerically explicit lower bound for 3-almost prime numbers which is asymptotic to Landau's formula, and hence to the actual count. It exceeds Landau's formula for all $x \geq 500194$. We prove an analogous lower bound for products of three distinct prime numbers. This expands on previously known results for $k \leq 2$.

1. Introduction

For a natural number *n*, the arithmetic functions $\omega(n)$ and $\Omega(n)$ denote the number of prime factors of *n*, counted without (respectively with) repeated prime factors. Thus for *n* with prime factorization $n = p_1^{a_1} \cdot \dots \cdot p_k^{a_k}$, we have $\omega(n) = k$ and $\Omega(n) = a_1 + \dots + a_k$.

Numbers *n* such that $\Omega(n) = k$ are called *k*-almost primes. Let $\pi_k(x) = |\{n \leq x : \omega(n) = \Omega(n) = k\}|$ denote the counting function of squarefree *k*-almost primes, and let $\tau_k(x) = |\{n \leq x : \Omega(n) = k\}|$ denote the counting function of *k*-almost primes.

For $k = 1$ we have $\pi_1(x) = \tau_1(x) = \pi(x)$, the prime counting function. The prime number theorem asserts that $\pi(x)$ is asymptotic to $x/\log x$. In 1900, Landau [6] proved that for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the estimate

$$\pi_k(x) = \frac{x(\log \log x)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!\log x} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{\log \log x}\right) \right)$$

holds, and that the same estimate also holds for $\tau_k(x)$.

Selberg [11] proved that for any $0 < \delta < 1$, uniformly for all $x \geq 3$ and $1 \leq k \leq (2 - \delta) \log \log x$, we have

$$\tau_k(x) = G\left(\frac{k-1}{\log \log x}\right) \frac{x(\log \log x)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!\log x} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{k}{(\log \log x)^2}\right) \right),$$

where

$$G(z) = F(1, z)/\Gamma(z + 1) \quad \text{and} \quad F(s, z) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{z}{p^s}\right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right)^z.$$

Classic references [5, 7] provide details on these and similar results. A 1962 paper [10] of Rosser and Schoenfeld and contemporary work [3, 4] of Dusart give explicit bounds for $\pi(x)$, see Lemma 1. A 2018 paper [1] of Bayless et al. established explicit upper bounds for $\pi_k(x)$, $\tau_2(x)$, and $\tau_3(x)$, as well as explicit lower bounds for $\pi_2(x)$ and $\tau_2(x)$. In particular, it is shown [1, Thm. 3.5] that for all $k \geq 2$ and $x \geq 3$, we have

$$\pi_k(x) \leq \frac{1.028x(\log \log x + 0.26153)^{k-1}}{(k - 1)! \log x},$$

and [1, Thm. 5.2] that for all $x \geq 10^{12}$, we have

$$\tau_2(x) \geq \pi_2(x) \geq \frac{x(\log \log x + 0.1769)}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{0.4232}{\log x}\right).$$

Furthermore [1, Thm. 5.3], for all $x \geq 10^{12}$ we have

$$\tau_3(x) \leq \frac{1.028x((\log \log x + 0.26153)^2 + 1.055852)}{2 \log x}.$$

A relatively sharp explicit lower bound for $\pi_3(x)$ requires more work, and aside from the explicit results above, the literature consists of implied constants. We prove explicit lower bounds for $\pi_3(x)$ and $\tau_3(x)$ which are asymptotic to Landau's formula, and hence to the actual count. In particular, we prove the following three theorems.

Theorem 1. *For all $x \geq 500194$,*

$$\tau_3(x) > \frac{x(\log \log x)^2}{2 \log x}.$$

The constant 500194 is optimal, since the inequality is violated at $x = 500194 - \epsilon$ for all sufficiently small $\epsilon > 0$. We also have an analogue of Theorem 1 for squarefree 3-almost primes, also called *sphenic numbers*.

Theorem 2. *For all $x \geq 10203553$,*

$$\pi_3(x) > \frac{x((\log \log x)^2 - 1)}{2 \log x}.$$

The constant 10203553 is also optimal. We also obtain the following.

Theorem 3. *For all sufficiently large x ,*

$$\pi_3(x) > \frac{x(\log \log x)^2}{2 \log x}.$$

Theorem 3 follows readily from the proof of Theorem 2 by comparing secondary terms, however the reader will see that x must be very large. Without more work, it is unclear where the optimal cutoff c_0 is for Theorem 3 to apply. Lifchitz and Renner [8] computed the values of $\pi_3(10^k)$ for $1 \leq k \leq 19$, and this data shows that $c_0 > 10^{19}$.

2. Notation and Preliminary Lemmas

Throughout the paper we let p, q , and r denote prime numbers and we let $\log x$ denote the natural logarithm. We define $L = \log \log x$, $x_0 = 10^{12}$, and $y_0 = x_0^{1/3} = 10^4$. Furthermore, $\pi(t)$ denotes the prime counting function and $T(t) = \sum_{p \leq t} 1/p$ denotes the sum of reciprocals of prime numbers $p \leq t$. We let $B = 0.2614972128\dots$ denote the *Mertens constant* and $c = 0.26146521$ (see Lemmas 2 and 3).

In bounding expressions, we will make use of manipulations such as

$$\log \log \frac{x}{a} = \log \log x + \log \left(1 - \frac{\log a}{\log x} \right),$$

the Maclaurin series expansion of the righthand term, and the bounds

$$\frac{1}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{\log a}{\log x} \right) < \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{a}} \leq \frac{1}{\log x} + \frac{1}{\log^2 x} \cdot \frac{\log a \log x_0}{\log \frac{x_0}{a}}$$

for $a > 1$ and $x \geq x_0$. We will use the following bounds [10, Thm. 2] of Rosser and Schoenfeld and [4, Cor. 5.2] of Dusart on the prime counting function.

Lemma 1 (Rosser, Schoenfeld, Dusart). *We have*

$$\frac{x}{\log x} < \pi(x)$$

for all $x \geq 17$. Additionally, we have

$$\frac{x}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log x} \right) \leq \pi(x) \leq \frac{x}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{1.2762}{\log x} \right),$$

where the lower bound holds for all $x \geq 599$ and the upper bound holds for all $x > 1$. Furthermore, for all $x > 1$ we have

$$\pi(x) \leq \frac{x}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log x} + \frac{2.53816}{\log^2 x} \right).$$

We also use the following bounds [10, Theorem 5] of Rosser and Schoenfeld and [3, Thm. 6.10], [4, Thm. 5.6] of Dusart which give numerically explicit versions of Mertens' second theorem.

Lemma 2 (Rosser, Schoenfeld, Dusart). *Let $T(t) = \sum_{p \leq t} 1/p$ denote the reciprocal sum of prime numbers up to t . We have*

$$T(t) = \log \log t + B + E(t),$$

where $B = 0.2614972128\dots$ denotes the Mertens constant, and

$$-\frac{1}{2 \log^2 t} < E(t) < \frac{1}{\log^2 t}$$

for all $t > 1$,

$$|E(t)| < \frac{1}{2 \log^2 t}$$

for all $t \geq 286$,

$$|E(t)| \leq \frac{1}{10 \log^2 t} + \frac{4}{15 \log^3 t}$$

for all $t \geq 10372$, and

$$|E(t)| \leq \frac{1}{5 \log^3 t}$$

for all $t \geq 2278383$.

Combining bounds on the prime number reciprocal sum in [10, 4] readily yields the following lower bound.

Lemma 3. *For $x > 1$,*

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p} > \log \log x + 0.26146521.$$

Proof. By Lemma 2, for all $x \geq 2278383$,

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p} \geq \log \log x + B - \frac{0.2}{\log^3 x}, \tag{1}$$

where B is the Mertens constant. By [10, Thm 20],

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p} > \log \log x + B$$

for all $x \leq 10^8$. Substituting 10^8 in (1) gives the lemma. □

3. The Proof of Theorem 2

We have

$$\pi_3(x) = |\{n = pqr \leq x : p < q < r\}|$$

where $p, q,$ and r denote prime numbers. To determine the count, we note the possible values for each of $p, q, r.$ We have $p < x^{1/3},$ and $q^2 < qr \leq x/p,$ so that $p < q < \sqrt{x/p}.$ Since $pqr \leq x,$ we also have $q < r \leq x/(pq).$ Therefore, $\pi_3(x)$ is equal to the sum of 1 over all possible values of $p, q, r,$ so that

$$\pi_3(x) = \sum_{p < x^{1/3}} \sum_{p < q < \sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \sum_{q < r \leq \frac{x}{pq}} 1 = \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \sum_{p < q \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \left(\pi\left(\frac{x}{pq}\right) - \pi(q) \right).$$

Here we have used the fact that the strict inequalities $p < x^{1/3}$ and $q < \sqrt{x/p}$ can be written to include the case of equality, since the quantity vanishes when $q = \sqrt{x/p}$ or when $p = x^{1/3}.$ We checked the inequality using the computer program Pari/GP for the interval $10203553 \leq x \leq 10^{12}.$ Thus we may assume $x \geq x_0.$ By Lemma 1, since $x/(pq) \geq 599$ we have

$$\pi\left(\frac{x}{pq}\right) \geq \frac{x}{pq \log \frac{x}{pq}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{pq}}\right) \geq \frac{x}{pq \log \frac{x}{pq}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log x}\right).$$

We thus have

$$\pi_3(x) \geq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log x}\right) \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_1 - \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_2,$$

where

$$S_1 = \sum_{p < q \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \frac{x}{pq \log \frac{x}{pq}}$$

and

$$S_2 = \sum_{p < q \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \pi(q).$$

We determine a lower bound for S_1 and an upper bound for $S_2.$ By Lemma 7 below, we have

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_2 \leq x \left(\frac{2L + 0.1436}{\log^2 x} + \frac{10.9113L + 3.1227}{\log^3 x} \right).$$

We next consider $S_1.$ We have

$$S_1 = \frac{x}{p} \sum_{p < q \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \frac{1}{q \log \frac{x}{q}}$$

where $y = x/p > x^{2/3} \geq x_0^{2/3}$. Recall that the function $T(t) = \sum_{p \leq t} 1/p$ denotes the prime reciprocal sum up to t . We bound S_1 below by applying partial summation to obtain

$$\sum_{p < q \leq \sqrt{y}} \frac{1}{q \log \frac{y}{q}} = \frac{T(\sqrt{y})}{\log \sqrt{y}} - \frac{T(p)}{\log \frac{y}{p}} - \int_p^{\sqrt{y}} \frac{T(t) dt}{t \log^2 \frac{y}{t}}. \tag{2}$$

By Lemma 2 this is bounded below by the expression

$$\frac{2(\log \log \sqrt{y} + B - \frac{1}{2 \log^2 \sqrt{y}})}{\log y} - \frac{\log \log p + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 p}}{\log \frac{y}{p}} - \int_p^{\sqrt{y}} \frac{\log \log t + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 t}}{t \log^2 \frac{y}{t}} dt.$$

Substituting $u = \log t$ and integrating, this is equal to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{-4}{\log^3 y} - \frac{\log \log p}{\log \frac{y}{p}} - \frac{1}{\log^2 p \log \frac{y}{p}} + \frac{\log \log \frac{y}{p}}{\log y} + \frac{\log p \log \log p}{\log y \log \frac{y}{p}} \\ & + \frac{1}{\log^2 y \log \frac{y}{p}} - \frac{1}{\log^2 y \log p} - \frac{2 \log \log \frac{y}{p}}{\log^3 y} + \frac{2 \log \log p}{\log^3 y}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus a lower bound for S_1 is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{x}{p \log \frac{x}{p}} \left(\log \log \frac{x}{p^2} + \frac{\log p \log \log p}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} + \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{p} \log \frac{x}{p^2}} + \frac{2 \log \log p}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \right) \\ & - \frac{x}{p \log \frac{x}{p}} \left(\frac{4}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} + \log \log p \cdot \frac{\log \frac{x}{p}}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} + \frac{1}{\log^2 p} \cdot \frac{\log \frac{x}{p}}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} + \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{p} \log p} + \frac{2 \log \log \frac{x}{p^2}}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

To simplify this expression, we compare the second (respectively, third) term of the first line above to the second (respectively, first) term of the second line. We have

$$\frac{\log p \log \log p}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} - \log \log p \cdot \frac{\log \frac{x}{p}}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} = -\log \log p.$$

Also, $1/(\log(x/p) \log(x/p^2)) > 1/\log^2(x/p)$. Therefore, a lower bound for expression (3) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{x}{p \log \frac{x}{p}} \left(\log \log \frac{x}{p^2} + \frac{2 \log \log p}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \right) \\ & - \frac{x}{p \log \frac{x}{p}} \left(\log \log p + \frac{3}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} + \frac{1}{\log^2 p} \cdot \frac{\log \frac{x}{p}}{\log \frac{x}{p^2}} + \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{p} \log p} + \frac{2 \log \log \frac{x}{p^2}}{\log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Write the sum of this expression over $p \leq x^{1/3}$ as

$$x(S_5 + S_6 - (S_7 + S_8 + S_9 + S_{10} + S_{11})).$$

Since $2 \log \log p - 3$ is negative for $p < 89$ and positive for $p \geq 89$,

$$\begin{aligned} S_6 - S_8 &= \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{2 \log \log p - 3}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\log^3 x} \sum_{p < 89} \frac{2 \log \log p - 3}{p} \frac{\log^3 x_0}{\log^3 \frac{x_0}{p}} + \frac{1}{\log^3 x} \sum_{89 \leq p \leq y_0} \frac{2 \log \log p - 3}{p} \\ &\geq \frac{-3.9322}{\log^3 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} S_{10} &= \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{1}{\log^2 x} \sum_{p \leq y_0} \frac{1}{p \log p \log^2 \frac{x_0}{p}} + \frac{2.25}{\log^2 x} \sum_{y_0 < p} \frac{1}{p \log p} \\ &\leq \frac{1.7496}{\log^2 x} + \frac{2.25(0.1085)}{\log^2 x} \\ &\leq \frac{1.9938}{\log^2 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we verified the value $\sum_p 1/(p \log p) = 1.63661\dots$ found to much higher precision [2, p. 6] by H. Cohen. Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} S_9 &= \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p \log \frac{x}{p^2}} \\ &\leq \sum_{p \leq y_0} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} \left(\frac{1}{\log x} + \frac{1}{\log^2 x} \frac{2 \log p \log x_0}{\log \frac{x_0}{p^2}} \right) + \frac{3}{\log x} \sum_{y_0 < p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} \\ &\leq \frac{1.5151}{\log x} + \frac{3.5585}{\log^2 x} + \frac{3}{\log x} \sum_{y_0 < p} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} \leq \frac{1.5328}{\log x} + \frac{3.5585}{\log^2 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we computed the sum over $y_0 < p \leq 10^9$ using Pari/GP and then applied partial summation together with Lemmas 2 and 3 to bound the sum over $p > 10^9$. By Lemma 8,

$$\begin{aligned} S_5 - S_7 &\geq \frac{0.5L^2 + 0.121434L - 0.22}{\log x} \\ &\quad + \frac{-1.5244L + 1.112}{\log^2 x} + \frac{-2L^2 + 2.9067L + 2.5389}{\log^3 x}, \end{aligned}$$

and by Lemma 5,

$$S_{11} \leq \frac{2L^2 + 1.3972L}{\log^3 x}.$$

Finally, note that the application of the bounds

$$L + c < T(x) < L + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 x},$$

valid for all $x > 1$, incur error terms which are particularly large for small values of x . We may improve our bounds as follows. In equation (2) we replaced the quantity $-T(p)/(p \log(x/p^2))$ with

$$-\frac{\log \log p + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 p}}{p \log \frac{x}{p^2}}.$$

Thus we may add the following expression to the lower bound:

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{\log \log p + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 p} - T(p)}{p \log \frac{x}{p^2}}.$$

A computation gives a lower bound of

$$\frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{4}} \sum_{p \leq y_0} \frac{\log \log p + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 p} - T(p)}{p} \geq \frac{0.9}{\log \frac{x}{4}} \geq \frac{0.9}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 4}{\log x} + \frac{\log^2 4}{\log^2 x} \right).$$

Again considering equation (2) and the following displayed expression, we may add to the lower bound

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \int_p^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{p}}} \frac{\log \log t + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 t} - T(t)}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{pt}} dt \\ & \geq \frac{1}{\log^2 x} \sum_{k \leq 1228} k \int_{\log p_k}^{\log p_{k+1}} \left(\log u + B + \frac{1}{u^2} - T(p_k) \right) du \\ & \geq \frac{20.4395}{\log^2 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Here p_k denotes the k -th prime number. Combining all bounds, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_3(x) & \geq \frac{x(0.5L^2 + 0.121434L - 0.8528)}{\log x} + \frac{x(0.5L^2 - 4L + 15)}{\log^2 x} \\ & \quad - \frac{x(4L^2 + 10.9262L)}{\log^3 x} \\ & \geq \frac{x(0.5L^2 + 0.121434L - 0.8528)}{\log x} + \frac{x(0.5L^2 - 4L + 12)}{\log^2 x} \tag{5} \\ & \geq \frac{x(0.5L^2 + 0.121434L - 0.8528)}{\log x} + \frac{4x}{\log^2 x} \\ & > \frac{x((\log \log x)^2 - 1)}{2 \log x} + \frac{4x}{\log^2 x} \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \geq x_0$. This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

4. Additional Lemmas

We prove several lemmas used in the proof of Theorem 2.

Lemma 4. *For $x \geq x_0$, we have*

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{L + 0.071781}{\log^2 x}.$$

Proof. For $x_0 \leq x \leq 10372^3$, we have

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{1}{\log^2 x} \sum_{p \leq 10372} \frac{\log^2 x_0}{p \log^2 \frac{x_0}{p}} \leq \frac{\log \log x_0 - 0.0279}{\log^2 x} \leq \frac{L}{\log^2 x},$$

by directly computing the sum over $p \leq 10372$. Suppose next that $x > 10372^3$. By Lemmas 2 and 3 and partial summation,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} &= \frac{T(x^{1/3})}{\log^2(x^{2/3})} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{2T(t) dt}{t \log^3 \frac{x}{t}} \\ &\leq \frac{\frac{9}{4}(\log \log x^{1/3} + 0.26300402)}{\log^2 x} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{2(\log \log t + c) dt}{t \log^3 \frac{x}{t}}, \end{aligned}$$

recalling that $c = 0.26146521$. The integral is equal to

$$\left[\frac{\log \log t + c}{\log^2 \frac{x}{t}} + \frac{\log \log \frac{x}{t} - \log \log t}{\log^2 x} - \frac{1}{\log x \log \frac{x}{t}} \right]_2^{x^{1/3}}.$$

Subtracting and bounding the resulting expression, we obtain

$$S_3 \leq \frac{\frac{9}{4}(0.26300402 - c) - \log 2 + \frac{1}{2} + c + \log \log \frac{x}{2}}{\log^2 x} \leq \frac{L + 0.071781}{\log^2 x}$$

for all $x \geq 10372^3$, and therefore for all $x \geq x_0$. □

Lemma 5. *For $x \geq x_0$, we have*

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{L + 0.6986}{\log^3 x}.$$

Proof. Note that for $x_0 \leq x \leq 10372^3$, we have

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \sum_{p \leq 10372} \frac{1}{p \log^3 x} \frac{\log^3 x_0}{\log^3 \frac{x_0}{p}} \leq \frac{L + 0.5411}{\log^3 x},$$

by directly computing the sum over $p \leq 10372$. Suppose next that $x \geq 10372^3$. By partial summation,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} &= \frac{T(x^{1/3})}{\log^3 x^{2/3}} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{3T(t) dt}{t \log^4 \frac{x}{t}} \\ &\leq \frac{\log \log x^{1/3} + 0.26300402}{\log^3 x^{2/3}} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{3(\log \log t + c) dt}{t \log^4 \frac{x}{t}}, \end{aligned}$$

using Lemmas 2 and 3. The integral is equal to

$$\left[\frac{\log \log t + c}{\log^3 \frac{x}{t}} + \frac{\log \log \frac{x}{t} - \log \log t}{\log^3 x} - \frac{1}{\log^2 x \log \frac{x}{t}} - \frac{1}{2 \log x \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} \right]_2^{x^{1/3}}.$$

Subtracting and bounding the resulting expression, we find that

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{\frac{27}{8}(0.26300402 - c) - \log 2 + \frac{9}{8} + \log \log \frac{x}{2} + c}{\log^3 x},$$

from which we obtain the lemma. □

Lemma 6. *For $x \geq x_0$ we have*

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{p} \log \frac{x}{p}} \leq \frac{0.4383x^{1/6}}{\log x}.$$

Proof. Let $x \geq x_0$. By partial summation,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{p} \log \frac{x}{p}} &\leq \frac{1.5}{\log x} \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} \\ &= \frac{1.5}{\log x} \left(\frac{\pi(x^{1/3})}{x^{1/6}} + \frac{1}{2} \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{\pi(t) dt}{t^{3/2}} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{1.5}{\log x} \left(\frac{\pi(x^{1/3})}{x^{1/6}} + 16.85461 + \frac{1}{2} \int_{y_0}^{x^{1/3}} \frac{\pi(t) dt}{t^{3/2}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 1, an upper bound for this expression is therefore

$$\frac{1.5}{\log x} \left(\frac{3.4154822x^{1/6}}{\log x} + 16.85461 + 0.06180521 \int_{y_0}^{x^{1/3}} \frac{dt}{t^{1/2}} \right),$$

from which the lemma readily follows. □

Lemma 7. For $x \geq x_0$ we have

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_2 \leq x \left(\frac{2L + 0.1436}{\log^2 x} + \frac{10.9113L + 3.1227}{\log^3 x} \right).$$

Proof. We have the general formula

$$\sum_{q \leq t} \pi(q) = 1 + 2 + \dots + \pi(t) = \frac{1}{2}(\pi(t)^2 + \pi(t)).$$

Therefore,

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\pi \left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{p}} \right)^2 + \pi \left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{p}} \right) - \pi(p)^2 - \pi(p) \right).$$

We will address the third term below and drop the fourth term. Let $x \geq x_0$. By Lemma 1, we have

$$\frac{1}{2} \pi \left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{p}} \right) \leq \frac{1.1385\sqrt{x}}{\sqrt{p} \log \frac{x}{p}}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{2} \pi \left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{p}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{2x}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} \left(1 + \frac{2.551155}{\log \frac{x}{p}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{2x}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} + \frac{10.9113x}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}}.$$

We thus have

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_2 \leq x \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \left(\frac{2}{p \log^2 \frac{x}{p}} + \frac{10.9113}{p \log^3 \frac{x}{p}} + \frac{1.1385}{\sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{p} \log \frac{x}{p}} \right).$$

Combining Lemmas 4, 5, and 6, we obtain

$$\sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} S_2 \leq x \left(\frac{2L + 0.1436}{\log^2 x} + \frac{10.9113L + 7.6227}{\log^3 x} + \frac{1.1}{\log^4 x} \right).$$

We now return to consider the remaining term:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \pi(p)^2 &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{\pi(x^{1/3})(\pi(x^{1/3}) + 1)(2\pi(x^{1/3}) + 1)}{6} \\ &\geq \frac{\pi(x^{1/3})^3}{6} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{x^{1/3}}{\log x^{1/3}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\log x^{1/3}} \right) \right)^3 \\ &\geq \frac{4.5x}{\log^3 x} \left(1 + \frac{9}{\log x} \right) \\ &= \frac{4.5x}{\log^3 x} + \frac{40.5x}{\log^4 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we have used Lemma 1. Combining these bounds, we obtain the lemma. \square

Lemma 8. For all $x \geq x_0$, we have

$$S_5 - S_7 \geq \frac{0.5L^2 + 0.121434L - 0.22}{\log x} + \frac{-1.5244L + 1.112}{\log^2 x} + \frac{-2L^2 + 2.9067L + 2.5389}{\log^3 x}.$$

Proof. Recall the definitions

$$S_5 = \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{\log \log \frac{x}{p^2}}{p \log \frac{x}{p}}, \quad S_7 = \sum_{p \leq x^{1/3}} \frac{\log \log p}{p \log \frac{x}{p}}.$$

We apply partial summation with $f(t) = \log \log \frac{x}{t^2} / \log \frac{x}{t}$ to obtain

$$S_5 = \frac{T(x^{1/3}) \log \log x^{1/3}}{\log x^{2/3}} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \log \log \frac{x}{t^2} dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} + \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{2T(t) dt}{t \log \frac{x}{t} \log \frac{x}{t^2}}.$$

We next apply partial summation with $g(t) = \log \log t / \log \frac{x}{t}$ to obtain

$$S_7 = \frac{T(x^{1/3}) \log \log x^{1/3}}{\log x^{2/3}} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \log \log t dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} - \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) dt}{t \log t \log \frac{x}{t}}.$$

Subtracting,

$$S_5 - S_7 = -I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4, \tag{6}$$

where

$$I_1 = \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \log \log \frac{x}{t^2} dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}},$$

$$I_2 = \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{2T(t) dt}{t \log \frac{x}{t} \log \frac{x}{t^2}},$$

$$I_3 = \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \log \log t dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}},$$

and

$$I_4 = \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) dt}{t \log t \log \frac{x}{t}}.$$

Let $x \geq x_0$. Splitting the interval at $x^{1/6}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\leq \left(L - \log \frac{3}{2}\right) \int_{x^{1/6}}^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t)}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt + L \int_2^{x^{1/6}} \frac{T(t)}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt \\ &\leq \left(L - \log \frac{3}{2}\right) \int_{x^{1/6}}^{x^{1/3}} \frac{\log \log t + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 t}}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt + L \int_2^{x^{1/6}} \frac{\log \log t + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 t}}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt \\ &= \left(L - \log \frac{3}{2}\right) \left(F(x^{1/3}) - F(x^{1/6})\right) + L \left(F(x^{1/6}) - F(2)\right) \\ &= L \left(F(x^{1/3}) - F(2)\right) - \left(\log \frac{3}{2}\right) \left(F(x^{1/3}) - F(x^{1/6})\right), \end{aligned}$$

where the antiderivative F is given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\log \log \frac{x}{t}}{\log x} + \frac{\log t \log \log t}{\log x \log \frac{x}{t}} + \frac{B}{\log \frac{x}{t}} + \frac{1}{\log^2 x \log \frac{x}{t}} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\log^2 x \log t} - \frac{2 \log \log \frac{x}{t}}{\log^3 x} + \frac{2 \log \log t}{\log^3 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Bounding the resulting expression gives

$$I_1 \leq \frac{0.5L^2 - 0.94565L + 0.1361}{\log x} + \frac{2.2153L}{\log^2 x} + \frac{2L^2 - 2.9067L - 2.0810}{\log^3 x},$$

where we made use of the identity

$$\log \log \frac{x}{2} = \log \log x + \log \left(1 - \frac{\log 2}{\log x}\right)$$

and bounded the Maclaurin series of the right term by comparison to a geometric series. We next bound

$$I_2 \geq \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{2(\log \log t + c) dt}{t \log \frac{x}{t} \log \frac{x}{t^2}} = \int_{\log 2}^{\log x^{1/3}} \frac{2(\log u + c) du}{(\log x - u)(\log x - 2u)}.$$

Integrating, a lower bound for I_2 is

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{2}{\log x} \left[\text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\log t}{\log x}\right) - \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\log t^2}{\log x}\right) + (\log \log t + c) \left(\log \log \frac{x}{t} - \log \log \frac{x}{t^2}\right) \right]_2^{x^{1/3}} \\ &= \frac{2}{\log x} \left(\text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) - \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) + (\log 2)(L - \log 3 + c) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{2}{\log x} \left(-\text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\log 2}{\log x}\right) + \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\log 4}{\log x}\right) + (\log \log 2 + c) \log \left(1 - \frac{\log 2}{\log \frac{x}{2}}\right) \right) \\ &\geq \frac{(\log 4)L - 2.0947}{\log x} + \frac{(\log 4)(1 - \log \log 2 - c)}{\log^2 x} + \frac{\log^2 2}{2 \log^3 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Here Li_2 denotes the dilogarithm, defined by the improper integral

$$\text{Li}_2(z) = - \int_0^z \frac{\log(1-t)}{t} dt.$$

For the terms $(\log 4)/\log^2 x + (\log^2 2)/(2\log^3 x)$ above, we have used the fact that the dilogarithm is concave up, together with the expansion

$$\text{Li}_2(z) = \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{z^k}{k^2}$$

for $|z| < 1$, putting $z = \log 2/\log x$, to bound

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Li}_2\left(\frac{\log 4}{\log x}\right) - \text{Li}_2\left(\frac{\log 2}{\log x}\right) &\geq \text{Li}_2\left(\frac{\log 4 - \log 2}{\log x}\right) - \text{Li}_2(0) \\ &= \text{Li}_2\left(\frac{\log 2}{\log x}\right) \geq \frac{\log 2}{\log x} + \frac{\log^2 2}{4\log^2 x}. \end{aligned}$$

We have also used the bound $-\log(1-z) \geq z$, here putting $z = \log 2/\log(x/2)$ and noting that $\log \log 2 + c < 0$.

We now turn to I_3 . In order to bound I_3 in the right direction, we write

$$I_3 = \int_2^e \frac{T(t) \log \log t \, dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} + \int_e^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \log \log t \, dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}}.$$

The first integral is equal to

$$\frac{1}{2 \log x} \left(\log \left(1 - \frac{1 - \log 2}{\log \frac{x}{2}} \right) - \frac{\log 2 \log \log 2}{\log \frac{x}{2}} \right) \geq \frac{-0.0304}{\log^2 x}.$$

A lower bound for the second integral is

$$\begin{aligned} \int_e^{x^{1/3}} \frac{(\log \log t + c) \log \log t \, dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} &= \int_1^{\log x^{1/3}} \frac{(\log u + c) \log u \, du}{(\log x - u)^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{\log x} \left[c \log \left(1 - \frac{u}{\log x} \right) + \frac{cu \log u}{\log x - u} + 2\text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{u}{\log x} \right) \right]_1^{\log x^{1/3}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\log x} \left[2(\log u) \log \left(1 - \frac{u}{\log x} \right) + \frac{u \log^2 u}{\log x - u} \right]_1^{\log x^{1/3}} \\ &\geq \frac{0.5L^2 - 1.77881L + 1.9771}{\log x} + \frac{c - 2}{\log^2 x} - \frac{0.5188}{\log^3 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Next, note that the use of the inequality $T(t) > \log \log t + c$ allows us to add to the

lower bound

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_3^{x^{1/3}} \frac{(T(t) - (\log \log t + c)) \log \log t \, dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} \\ & \geq \frac{1}{\log^2 \frac{x}{3}} \sum_{2 \leq k \leq 1228} \int_{\log p_k}^{\log p_{k+1}} (T(p_k) - c - \log u) \log u \, du \\ & \geq \frac{0.3099}{\log^2 x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 9}{\log x} \right). \end{aligned}$$

We therefore have

$$I_3 \geq \frac{0.5L^2 - 1.77881L + 1.9771}{\log x} - \frac{1.4591}{\log^2 x} + \frac{0.1621}{\log^3 x}.$$

We now consider

$$I_4 = \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) \, dt}{t \log t \log \frac{x}{t}} \geq \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{(\log \log t + c) \, dt}{t \log t \log \frac{x}{t}} = \int_{\log 2}^{\log x^{1/3}} \frac{(\log u + c) \, du}{u(\log x - u)}.$$

Integrating, we obtain the expression

$$\frac{1}{\log x} \left[c \log u - (\log u) \log \left(1 - \frac{u}{\log x} \right) - c \log(\log x - u) - \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{u}{\log x} \right) + \frac{\log^2 u}{2} \right]_{\log 2}^{\log x^{1/3}}.$$

We bound this expression to obtain

$$I_4 \geq \frac{0.5L^2 - 0.4317L - 0.3608}{\log x} + \frac{0.7658}{\log^2 x} + \frac{0.0556}{\log^3 x}.$$

Note that the inequality $T(t) > \log \log t + c$ was used to bound I_4 . We may therefore add the following expression to the lower bound:

$$\int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) - (\log \log t + c)}{t \log t \log \frac{x}{t}} dt \geq \frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{2}} \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) - (\log \log t + c)}{t \log t} dt.$$

Splitting the interval $[2, y_0]$ into subintervals between primes $[p_k, p_{k+1}]$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, 1228$, and using the numerical value of $T(p_k)$ in each subinterval, we find by computation in Pari/GP that

$$\frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{2}} \int_2^{x^{1/3}} \frac{T(t) - (\log \log t + c)}{t \log t} dt \geq \frac{0.3945}{\log \frac{x}{2}} \geq \frac{0.3945}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 2}{\log x} \right).$$

A similar argument allows us to improve our upper bound on the integral I_1 in equation (6). Here we used the upper bound

$$L \int_2^{x^{1/6}} \frac{T(t)}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt \leq L \int_2^{x^{1/6}} \frac{\log \log t + B + \frac{1}{\log^2 t}}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t}} dt.$$

Bounding the difference in the interval $[2, 100]$, we add $0.6909L/\log^2 x$ to the lower bound. Combining the bounds for I_1, I_2, I_3 , and I_4 completes the proof of Lemma 8. \square

5. The Proof of Theorem 1

We now prove Theorem 1. Note that $\tau_3(x) = \pi_3(x) + N(x)$, where $N(x) = |\{n \leq x : n = p^2q\}|$, and p and q denote (possibly equal) primes. For each such p , the number of possibilities for q is $\pi(x/p^2)$, and we thus have

$$N(x) = \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right).$$

The range $500194 \leq x \leq 10^{12}$ was checked using the computer program Pari/GP. Thus we may assume $x \geq x_0$. Now, a lower bound for $\pi_3(x)$ is given in Theorem 2. The contribution from $N(x)$ is given by the following lemma, from which Theorem 1 follows by an argument analogous to that of inequality (5) in the proof of Theorem 2.

Lemma 9. *For all $x \geq x_0$ we have*

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right) \geq x \left(\frac{\alpha}{\log x} + \frac{0.9861}{\log^2 x} + \frac{1.2861}{\log^3 x} \right),$$

where $\alpha = \sum_p 1/p^2 = 0.4522474\dots$ denotes the reciprocal sum of squares of primes.

Proof. Let $x \geq x_0$. We wish to apply the lower bound $\pi(t) > t/\log t$, valid for $t \geq 17$, in Lemma 1. Thus we write

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right) = \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right) + \sum_{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}} < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right).$$

The right sum is

$$\sum_{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}} < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}} \pi\left(\frac{x}{p^2}\right) = -6 \cdot \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}\right) + \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{13}}\right) + \dots + \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}\right).$$

Also by Lemma 1, this expression is bounded below by

$$2\sqrt{x} \left(-6 \cdot \frac{1.0972}{\sqrt{17} \log \frac{x}{17}} + \sum_{k=1}^6 \frac{1}{\sqrt{p_k} \log \frac{x}{p_k}} \right) \geq \frac{1.8188\sqrt{x}}{\log x},$$

where p_k denotes the k -th prime number. For the remaining term, let $S(t) = \sum_{p \leq t} (1/p^2)$. By partial summation,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{1}{p^2 \log \frac{x}{p^2}} &= \frac{S(\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}})}{\log 17} - \int_2^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{2S(t) dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t^2}} \\ &= \frac{S(\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}})}{\log 17} - \int_2^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{2\alpha dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t^2}} + \int_2^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{2(\alpha - S(t)) dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\int_2^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{2\alpha dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t^2}} = \frac{\alpha}{\log 17} - \frac{\alpha}{\log \frac{x}{4}} \leq \frac{\alpha}{\log 17} - \frac{\alpha}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 4}{\log x}\right).$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_2^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{2(\alpha - S(t)) dt}{t \log^2 \frac{x}{t^2}} &\geq \sum_{k \leq 21433} (\alpha - S(p_k)) \left[\frac{1}{\log \frac{x}{t^2}}\right]_{p_k}^{p_{k+1}} \\ &= \sum_{k \leq 21433} (\alpha - S(p_k)) \frac{\log \frac{p_{k+1}^2}{p_k^2}}{\log \frac{x}{p_{k+1}^2} \log \frac{x}{p_k^2}} \\ &\geq \frac{0.3592}{\log \frac{x}{9} \log \frac{x}{4}} \\ &\geq \frac{0.3592}{\log^2 x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 9}{\log x}\right) \left(1 + \frac{\log 4}{\log x}\right) \\ &\geq \frac{0.3592}{\log^2 x} + \frac{1.2872}{\log^3 x}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{1}{p^2 \log(\frac{x}{p^2})} \geq \frac{\alpha}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{\log 4}{\log x}\right) + \frac{0.3592}{\log^2 x} + \frac{1.2872}{\log^3 x} - \frac{1}{\log 17} \sum_{p > \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{1}{p^2}.$$

By [9, Lem. 2.7], we have

$$\frac{1}{\log 17} \sum_{p > \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} \frac{1}{p^2} < \frac{1/\log 17}{\sqrt{\frac{x}{17}} \log \sqrt{\frac{x}{17}}} = \frac{2\sqrt{17}/\log 17}{\sqrt{x} \log \frac{x}{17}} \leq \frac{3.2431}{\sqrt{x} \log x}.$$

Combining these bounds, we obtain Lemma 9. □

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